

National and international dimensions of research: Topics of local and global interest in scientific production

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Abstract

This study aims at identifying and comparing the national scope of research at the country level of two groups of countries: LAC and World. We want to explore whether similar or different patterns arise between the two groups at the global and disciplinary level in their proportion of research related to local perspectives or topics. Findings show that LAC countries present a greater proportion of local production than the rest of the countries. The trend to publish national-oriented research is related to disciplinary fields and it is not only coarsened into national but in extra regional journals. Even though English is the dominant language of publication, the lingua franca is more likely to appear in the national scope of research, especially for LAC countries but also in the rest of non-Anglophone countries. Some implications in research evaluation for further research are described.

Introduction

There exist disparities globally when it comes to knowledge production and research capacities of countries, - limited access to research funding and opportunities in some countries (Demeter 2020). The modes of the knowledge production and circulation are affected by numerous factors, among them the geographic realm of research and disquisitions among the local, regional, national, and international scales, i.e., the simultaneous dimensions of activity (Marginson 2022). While national research agendas focus on both, development of strategic global topics to solve complex problems and topics oriented to the resolution of local issues, global geopolitics can also influence the development of scientific knowledge in local, national and regional contexts (Bennet 2014). Then the geographic scope of research may be seen as a valuable aspect of scientific development that helps orient agendas for science, technology, and innovation, while demonstrating the interest in certain “national” topics far beyond the domestic borders.

Traditionally, national scientific production is delimited as the contribution made by each country to the stock of worldwide scientific knowledge, using as a selection criterion the geographical origin of institutional affiliation of the publications’ authors. This conceptualization and its operationalization are usually used to benchmark the performance of national research systems. However, most studies are led by researchers based in the global north, even when they focus on a country or region in the global south (Amarante et al 2021), while there is a tension in the global south for dependencies of mainstream science to develop national research agendas of countries (Vessuri et al 2014). In this context, the extent to which national-oriented research about natural resources, economic, health or social issues inherent to their own territories is carried out by different countries has been less explored.

Some studies have analyzed the geographical realm of research considering coauthorship and topics of local interest among Colombian research groups revealing that this research contributes to the local stock of information necessary to increase local understanding and to produce new knowledge valuable to solve local intellectual, technical and/or social issues

(Ordoñez-Matamoros et al, 2010). Others have explored specific aspects of the local character of research, like the interdisciplinarity in the Colombian scientific production (Chavarro, et al 2014). Most studies analyzing local vs global topics of interests have focused in Argentinean research from the point of view of its disciplinary breakdown (Miguel, et al, 2015a); factors affecting the visibility of social sciences research (Miguel et al, 2015b); the use of natural language and non-supervised algorithms for detecting research topics (González et al, 2017; González et al, 2018; González y Varela, 2019); using different data sources, like SciELO and Scopus (Hidalgo, et al, 2019); analyzing coverage and overlapping in different data sources for research focused on a specific geographic area (Arias y González, 2021); studying patterns of international collaboration in both, local and global topics of interest in Agroindustry research (González y Chinchilla Rodríguez, 2019; González y Chinchilla Rodríguez, 2020). At the global level, Castro-Torres and Albúrez-Gutiérrez (2022) analyze how the names of countries appear in the title and abstract of publications (naming practices) in the field of social sciences arguing that peripheral countries are more likely to use these practices than mainstream countries. All these studies are based on the identification of toponyms in publications. No studies were found showing the global and disciplinary patterns of national scope for other countries.

This study focuses on the scientific production of a group of countries in the Latin American and Caribbean region (LAC), considered to be on the scientific periphery, and on the comparison with another group of countries that are at the forefront in the development of mainstream science (including non-English speaking countries). Our hypothesis lies on those LAC countries present a particular pattern of knowledge production with a strong trend to deal with issues of local interest published in national journals in lingua franca. It may be seen as a “brand of identity” which differentiates these countries from those of the global north. Therefore, this study aims to a) identify and compare the national scope at the country level of the two groups: LAC and World, b) explore whether similar or different patterns arise between the two groups of countries at the global and disciplinary level, and c) analyze journals and language of publications.

Data and methods

Our sample includes two distinct groups composed by the most prolific countries for the period 2009-2018. For the LAC group, we consider Brasil, México, Argentina, Chile, Colombia, Cuba, Venezuela, Perú, Ecuador and Uruguay. For the WORLD group: Estados Unidos, China, Reino Unido, Alemania, Japón, Francia, India, Italia, Canadá y España. Data was retrieved using Scopus database which offers a broad geographic and thematic coverage for peripheral countries than Web of Science (Moya-Anegón et al 2007; Singh et al 2021).

Three search strategies were established to obtain two separate groups of data: 1) using the AFFILCOUNTRY field, we retrieved the total documents published for each of the 20 countries considering all document types. 2) For each country, we search the name of the country or demonym in titles and keywords, for example, (AFFILCOUNTRY (Argentina) AND (TITLE (argentin*) OR KEY (argentin*))) AND PUBYEAR >2008 AND PUBYEAR < 2019. We do not consider the abstract field because it includes country names in the context of a copyright statement (e.g., “© Akadémiai Kiadó, Budapest, Hungary 2014”) that are not relevant for this study. 3) The remaining set of records, in which the name of the country did not appear. Accordingly, the first strategy gives us all documents published by each country. In the second strategy, we identify ‘topics of national scope’, whereas the third one was designated as ‘topics of global scope’. Our sample includes more than 18 million documents.

Disciplinary breakdown was established following the 27 subject areas provided by the All Science Journal Classification (ASJC). Then, we grouped them into 6 broad scientific fields according to the Frascati Manual classification (OECD 2015). To determine the publication patterns in national journals for both groups, LAC and WORLD group, we identify the geographical region of publishers. For each country, the following indicators were calculated: total number of documents; number and percentage of documents of national scope (NS); number and percentage of documents of global scope (GS); percentage of NS and GS documents by broad scientific fields; percentage of documents published in national and non national journals; percentage of documents published in English and percentage of documents published in lingua franca (for those non-Anglophones countries). Full counts were used to identify the total number of publications per country.

Results

We find that, although articles of the World group dominate our sample (Figure1), LAC countries are more prone to publish national-oriented research (21.5% on average) than the rest of countries (7.8% on average).

Figure 1. Total number of documents (grey color scale) and percentage of national and global scope (orange circles) per country.

Figure 2. Average growth rate of documents of national and global scope.

However, the average growth rate of NS documents is higher for LAC countries (6.3%) than for the WORLD group (3.4%), as well as in GS (Figure 2). This increase may be due to different scientific capacities and phases of development – less productive countries tend to grow more than most productive and consolidated countries. Ecuador (18%), Peru (11%), Colombia (10%) present the highest growth in NS followed by China (8%) and India (6%); except for Venezuela and USA, NS research growth is faster than GS for all countries. On the other hand, Mexico, USA and Canada show a higher growth in the global (GS) production than in NS.

Unsurprisingly, arts and humanities as well as social sciences in general, and economics and business in particular are those disciplines with a strong component of national-oriented research – i.e., documents with geographical reference to the country (NS)-, following by agricultural, veterinary, earth and environmental sciences (Figure 3). Although the proportion of NS research is uneven among countries, nursing, clinical medicine and immunology stand out in medical and health sciences, in some LAC countries: Ecuador, Peru and Venezuela and in the WORLD group: China, India and Japan.

Figure 3. Percentage of national-oriented documents by 27 subject areas ASJC (Scopus) grouped by the 7 broad scientific fields defined by the Frascati Manual

In all LAC countries (Figure 4A), the percentage of documents in the lingua franca is higher than English in NS research, as well as in Germany, France, Italy and Spain. In Japan, we observed the same proportion of English and Japanese publications in both, NS and GS research. While China and Canada show the opposite patterns, Chinese and French are more used in GS than in NS research (Figure 4B).

Figure 4. English vs. lingua franca in LAC countries (A) and WORLD countries (B) for local (%NS) vs. global scope research (%GS). Percentages may be exceeding 100% due to documents published in more than one language.

LAC research is mostly published in journals from Latin America, Western Europe and North America (Tables 1 and 2). The strong presence of journals from these last two regions is not surprising – they accumulate 73% of journals indexed in Scopus. However, it is worthy to mention that although the share of LAC journals in Scopus is only 3.4%, regional journals play an important role in disseminating national scope research in LAC countries. Besides, although with low proportions of NS documents, this production is also published in journals from Asia and the Pacific regions. Venezuela, Colombia, Cuba, Brazil and Chile show a higher proportion of documents geographically situated (NS), while Ecuador and Uruguay show the opposite pattern.

Table 1. Topics of national scope and main publishers

Region	Brasil	México	Argentina	Chile	Colombia	Cuba	Venezuela	Perú	Ecuador	Uruguay
Latin America	44.4	34.8	28.4	43.8	47.3	46.4	50.0	28.1	14.9	19.3
Western Europe	34.3	38.7	46.5	38.8	32.2	30.9	30.1	39.7	44.6	49.1
Northern America	16.6	21.7	20.2	15.1	16.9	19.3	15.6	28.3	34.1	26.5
Pacific Region	3.1	1.7	2.9	1.1	2.2	1.2	1.9	1.6	3.6	3.18
Eastern Europe	0.7	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.4	0.8	0.7	0.5	1.3	0.34
Asiatic Region	0.6	1.5	0.7	0.4	0.6	1.3	1.6	2.0	1.2	0.17
Middle East	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.92
Africa	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.46

Table 2. Topics of global scope and main publishers

Región	Brasil	México	Argentina	Chile	Colombia	Cuba	Venezuela	Perú	Ecuador	Uruguay
Latin America	30.8	15.2	14.1	20.8	30.4	34.4	33.1	22.7	10.3	9.04
Western Europe	38.0	45.4	51.5	46.2	38.3	22.4	36.5	56.7	46.8	54.6
Northern America	27.0	33.0	30.2	29.2	26.9	10.0	25.8	40.4	38.3	32.54
Pacific Region	0.6	0.4	0.8	0.3	0.6	0.2	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.05
Eastern Europe	0.8	1.8	1.0	1.1	0.9	0.3	1.2	0.9	0.9	0.85
Asiatic Region	1.5	2.4	1.4	1.4	1.7	1.0	1.4	1.7	1.7	0.60
Middle East	0.6	0.8	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.4	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.81
Africa	0.5	1.1	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.1	0.7	0.6	0.5	0.48

Conclusions

The results show that there are different patterns in the production of research of national scope between the two groups. LAC countries present a greater proportion of local production than the rest of the countries (World Group) which is partially in consonance with Castro-Torres and Albúrez-Gutiérrez (2022). For all countries, even if English is the dominant language of publication, the lingua franca is more likely to appear in the national scope of research, especially for LAC countries but also in the rest of non-Anglophone countries. Findings focused on LAC countries suggest that the trend to publish national-oriented research is related to disciplinary fields and it is not only coarsened into national but in extra regional journals.

These findings have practical implications. First, criteria implicit in quantitative evaluation methods are often biased against research related to local perspectives or topics, then peripheral countries tend to disadvantage research that matters for local issues (Rafols, et al 2016). Hence, national-oriented research should not be underrated because it may be of interest not just for the own country but for research communities based far from the country that generates this type of knowledge. Second, the current landscape of knowledge diffusion becomes an opportunity to globalize national-oriented research in non-Anglophone countries and minimize the tension between national and international dimensions of knowledge production. Ideas are needed on how to create a more inclusive environment for researchers working in the non-Anglophone countries: proficiency in English, improvement of editorial quality of national journals, South-North collaborations could be an avenue for change, etc. (Amarante et al 2022).

Third, to better understand the dynamics of the global system of science, it is necessary to have information generated from different approaches, including the geographic realm of research, to know to what extent countries deal with problems of their own territory. Further research should be needed to delve into the nature and dynamics of research oriented to local issues and its relationship with evaluation criteria and research agendas. This approach could be extended to different countries breaking down to more specific levels (regions, districts, etc.) (Miguel, et al 2015). Although the geographical realm in the scientific discourse does not always coincide with administrative units like regions or districts (Matthiessen et al, 2010), this research poses new conceptual and methodological challenges for the study of national-oriented research at the country level.

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